

1 **APC is a tumor suppressor and its deletion results in ECT2 induction in vivo.**

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6 Tumor suppressors have as of yet been identified based on their ability to restrict transformation when
7 expressed or their ability to support transformation when mutated or deleted (when their expression is
8 lost). We identified ECT2 as a major solid tumor gene product and established at length that its
9 expression is a function of the transformed state and controlled by the tumor suppressors p53 and Rb1
10 indicating its utility in identification of *bona fide* tumor suppressors. APC has been described as a tumor
11 suppressor. We studied total transcription in the liver and in the gastrointestinal tract following in vivo
12 deletion of APC. The data indicate with confidence that APC is a tumor suppressor, with functional
13 capacity equivalent to that of p53 and/or Rb1.
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Results

We assessed 1) whether ECT2 induction was a universal quality of tumor suppressor impairment, like we demonstrated previously following deletion or mutation of *p53* and *Rb1*; and, given our presumed (hypothesized) understanding ECT2 induction in transformation 2) whether APC could properly be classified or characterized as a bona fide tumor suppressor, by measuring ECT2 induction using published microarray data to measure total transcription in genetically engineered mice with deletion of APC, in the intestine and in the liver.

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n=7 whole intestine, control mice (wild-type; C57BL/6J)

n=3 whole intestine, mice with genetically engineered villin-Cre Apc deletion (fl/fl; Cre+)

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
1419513_a_at	1.21E-05	-7.2917509	3.643729	-1.1648018	Ect2	703/44944	98.4
1420957_at	8.91E-02	1.8569442	-5.223344	0.1688272	Apc	18295/44944	59.3

GSE65476

n=3 whole liver, control mice (wild-type; fl/fl)

n=3 whole liver, mice with genetically engineered Ah-Cre Apc deletion (fl/fl; Cre+)

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
1419513_a_at	7.89E-05	-9.64	2.319969	-1.7	Ect2	212/32176	99.3
1435543_at	3.54E-02	2.72	-4.164254	3.02E-01	Apc	6073/32176	81.1

In both the liver and the intestine, Apc deletion resulted in ECT2 induction with a magnitude of activation that resembled that following loss of Rb1 and p53 in human cells and *in vivo* in mice. Apc exerted tumor suppressor function in the gastrointestinal tract, as previously described, as well as outside in the intestinal tissues, in the liver. We concluded that ECT2 induction was a universal marker of tumor suppressor loss, that APC was a bona fide tumor suppressor, and that APC exerted tumor suppressor function in multiple tissues, in the intestines as previously understood, as well as in the liver.

Discussion

We demonstrated here using whole transcriptome data from genetically engineered animal models of tissue-restricted Apc loss that Apc is a tumor suppressor, in the GI tract and in the liver, and that ECT2 is indeed a universal and direct transcriptional consequence (marker) of impairment or loss of tumor suppressor function. The data provide further evidence supporting a clear function for ECT2-based imaging to detect in a sensitive and specific manner the emergence of transformation (solid tumor disease - cancer) in the public as a surveillance and cancer interception technique. Thus, the observation that ECT2 is a transcriptional feature of cancer of the solid tissues in humans (i.e., differentially expressed in all solid tumors in humans at 1-10% differential expression transcriptome-wide) is a direct consequence of ECT2 induction as a result of tumor suppression impairment.